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Redescription of *Aphaenogaster kurdica* Ruzsky, 1905 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmicinae)

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Abstract: *Aphaenogaster kurdica* Ruzsky, 1905, a member of the *A. graeca* species-group is redescribed based on material collected in the Golestan Province of northern Iran. A key to species of the *Aphaenogaster graeca* group is given.

Key words: ants, northern Iran, taxonomy, redescription.

INTRODUCTION

Aphaenogaster MAYR, 1853 is a worldwide genus, which includes 217 valid species and subspecies (BOLTON 2024). Among them, almost 100 taxa are known from Europe (including Caucasian countries), the Mediterranean Basin, and the Middle East up to eastern Iran (KIRAN *et al.* 2008, BOER 2013, BOROWIEC 2014, BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014, 2018, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2016, 218, GÓMEZ *et al.* 2018, ALICATA & SCHIFANI 2019, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2019, BRAČKO *et al.* 2019, GALKOWSKI *et al.* 2019, SALATA *et al.* 2021, SCHIFANI & ALICATA 2023, ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024). SCHULZ (1994) proposed the first modern division of some west Palearctic taxa of *Aphaenogaster* that later was supplemented and modified in several taxonomic studies (e.g., KIRAN *et al.* 2008, BOER 2013, BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2018, ALICATA & SCHIFANI 2019, ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024). Finally, based on morphological and molecular data of most of the European *Aphaenogaster* species, SCHIFANI *et al.* (2022) proposed a new species group division of West-Palearctic *Aphaenogaster*. Among novelties, the authors established a new species group, named the *A. graeca* species group that included three species: *A. aktaci* KIRAN & TEZCAN, 2008, *A. graeca* SCHULZ, 1994, and *A. illyrica* BRAČKO *et al.*, 2019. The group is characterized by the following combination of characters: coloration dark brown to reddish, body elongate, appendages long, mesonotum well demarcated, medium-sized spines with a thick base, horizontal or very slightly curved upwards, mesonotum clearly rising above the surface of pronotum and separated by a strong promesonotal suture (*A. graeca*, *A. illyrica*) or propodeal dorsum lacking transverse surface sculpturing (*A. aktaci*). The group is considered to inhabit Anatolia and the Balkans.

Recently, we had an occasion to study two series of specimens collected in the Golestan province of northern Iran with characters typical for members of the *Aphaenogaster graeca* species group. Examination of the descriptions of poorly known taxa of *Aphaenogaster* described from the Caucasus and Iran led us to the conclusion that the freshly collected specimens represent *A. kurdica* RUZSKY, 1905. The taxonomic status and species group affiliation of this species were enigmatic and recently briefly discussed by ZIECINA *et al.* (2024). This species was described as a subspecies of *A. subterranea* from the border of Armenia and Azerbaijan (Elisabethpol district, now Gandja, Zangezur Mts.). Although the description of this taxon is quite comprehensive, the only characteristics that distinguish it from the nominotypical subspecies are the mesonotum clearly rising above the surface of the pronotum and the poorly sculptured, shiny upper half of the head. Later, EMERY (1908), having syntypes of *A. subterranea kurdica* at his disposal, made a short redescription and a schematic drawing of the mesosoma and transferred this taxon to the rank of a subspecies of *A. smythiesi*, a taxon described from India but widely distributed from Afghanistan to South Korea. In the redescription Emery also noted that the mesonotum of *A. kurdica* is clearly raised above the pronotum and that strongly separates this taxon from *A. subterranea*. This character is also clearly visible in the drawing. Afterward, already as a species, *A. kurdica* was recorded from a few localities in Azerbaijan (ARNOLDI 1948), Armenia (ARAKELIAN 1994), Georgia (GRATIASHVILI & BARJADZE 2008), Iran (PAKNIA *et al.* 2013), and Caucasian Russia (DUBOVIKOFF & YUSUPOV 2017). Unfortunately, none of these publications provided any additional insights on the morphology of the species. Most likely the type specimens of this taxon are stored at Zoological Museum of Moscow University and are currently unavailable for studies. Due to the fact that our specimens from Iran show the characters given in the original description and redescription authored by EMERY (1908), we conclude that these specimens most likely belong to *Aphaenogaster kurdica* and we provide its detailed redescription below.

STUDY AREA, MATERIAL, AND METHODS

Investigated specimens, from a single site, were collected in Tuskestan Forest in the Golestan Province. This forest represents an eastern part of Hyrcanian Forest extending along the shores of the Caspian Sea from Azerbaijan to the north-eastern Iran. Tuskestan forest is located in the northeastern slopes of Alborz Mountains, 13 kilometers southeast of Gorgan city, on the route from Gorgan to Shahroud.

All specimens were preserved in 75% EtOH. Photos were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1500 stereomicroscope, Nikon D5200 photo camera, and Helicon Focus software.

Collection abbreviations:

DPPGU – Department of Plant Protection, Gorgan University of Agricultural Sciences and Natural Resources;

MNHW – Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, Poland;

MHNG – Muséum d'Historie Naturelle, Genève, Switzerland.

Measurements (all measurements are given in mm):

EL – eye length; measured along the maximum vertical diameter of eye;

HFL – hind femur length; measured from ventral end of trochanter to dorsal end of femur;

HL – head length; measured in straight line from mid-point of anterior clypeal margin to mid-point of posterior cephalic margin in full-face view;

HFL – hind tibia length; measured from dorsal margin of base to posterior margin;
HW – head width; measured in full-face view directly above the eyes;
MD – Malar distance. Minimum distance from the anterior margin of the compound eye to where the mandible articulates with the head capsule;
ML – mesosoma length; measured as diagonal length from the anterior end of the neck shield to the posterior margin of the propodeal lobe;
MW – mesosoma width (= pronotum width); maximum width of pronotum in dorsal view;
PH – petiole height; the chord of ventral petiolar profile at node level is the reference line perpendicular to which the maximum height of petiole is measured;
PL – petiole length; length of the petiolar node, measured in lateral view from petiolar spiracle to dorso-caudal corner of caudal cylinder;
PPW – postpetiole width; maximum width of postpetiole in dorsal view;
PW – petiole width; maximum width of petiole in dorsal view;
PSL – propodeal spine length; measured from the centre of the propodeal spiracle to the tip of the propodeal spine in lateral view;
SL – scape length; maximum straight-line length of scape excluding the articular condyle.

RESULTS

Aphaenogaster kurdica RUZSKY, 1905

Aphaenogaster subterranea ssp. *kurdica* RUZSKY, 1905: 717.

Aphaenogaster smythiesi ssp. *kurdica*: EMERY 1908: 332.

Aphaenogaster kurdica: ARNOLDI 1948: 211.

Redescription of worker

Material examined: 12 workers, IRAN, Golestan, Gorgan suburbs, 683 m, 36.73883 / 54.56679, 29 IV 2022, leg. Fakhteh Jafari (DPPGU, MHNG, MNHW).

Measurements and ratios (n = 12): **HL:** 1.206 (1.04–1.33), **HW:** 1.002 (0.83–1.14), **EL:** 0.216 (0.19–0.25), **SL:** 1.252 (1.10–1.37), **MD:** 0.336 (0.26–0.37), **ML:** 1.677 (1.41–1.94), **MW:** 0.652 (0.54–0.75), **PSL:** 0.255 (0.18–0.32), **PL:** 0.491 (0.43–0.54), **PH:** 0.311 (0.26–0.35), **PW:** 0.251 (0.20–0.29), **PPW:** 0.313 (0.25–0.37), **HFL:** 1.432 (1.24–1.59), **HTL:** 1.007 (0.86–1.18), **HL/HW:** 1.205 (1.174–1.247), **SL/HW:** 1.252 (1.203–1.324), **SL/HL:** 1.039 (1.024–1.070), **EL/HL:** 0.179 (0.166–0.192), **ML/MW:** 2.573 (2.496–2.666), **PSL/HW:** 0.253 (0.220–0.279), **PL/PH:** 1.593 (1.477–1.684), **PPW/PW:** 1.250 (1.184–1.324), **HFL/ML:** 0.847 (0.794–0.889).

Body colouration. Head, mesosoma, petiole, and postpetiole from predominantly yellow to mostly ochraceous yellow with yellowish brown to rusty brown head and mesosoma, anterior part of frons and mandibles orange yellow to rusty yellow, antennae from uniformly yellow or with antennal scapi ochraceous yellow. First gastral tergite completely yellow or partly yellowish brown, with yellowish base and apex. Legs yellow (Figs. 1-6). **Head.** Approximately 1.17-1.25 x as long as wide, lateral margins in full-face view evenly rounded, occipital corners rounded, posterior margin straight (Figs. 3, 4). Anterior margin of clypeus shallowly emarginated. Eyes small, approximately 0.17-0.19 x as long as head length, placed in the middle of lateral margin of head (Fig. 4). Scape moderately elongate, 1.2-1.3 x as long as head width, at base twice narrower than at apex, then gradually widened, without preapical constriction. Funiculus approximately 1.4 times as long as scape, first segment moderately

elongated, 2.4 times as long as wide at apex, 0.75 x as long as two subsequent segments combined, segments 2-6 short, 1.2-1.3 x as long as wide, segments 8-10 approximately 1.6 x as long as wide, last 4 segments forming an indistinct club, approximately as long as basal funicular segments 1-7 combined. Mandibles elongate, with distinct striation and with some elongate punctures but shiny, masticatory margin with 7-8 teeth. Clypeus surface smooth and shiny or in the middle with diffused microreticulation, without median keel but with three longitudinal rugae on each side. Frontal carinae moderately elongate, partly surrounding frontal cavities, frontal triangle deeply impressed with median keel and smooth and shiny background. Frons in the narrowest part as wide as 0.26 width of head, along the middle without or with indistinct elevated keel, on sides with 3-4 longitudinal rugae, interspaces diffusely microreticulated, shiny. Antennal cavities margined by regular, circular rugae, interspaces smooth and shiny. Central part of head dorsum between eyes with mostly sparse, partly longitudinal and partly irregular rugae, extending to 1/2-2/3 length of head, area between rugae diffusely microreticulated and shiny. Posterior 1/3 length of head smooth and shiny or partly diffusely, indistinctly microreticulated, occiput completely smooth and shiny. Antennal scape with fine microreticulation and few thin, longitudinal rugae but surface appears shiny. **Mesosoma.** Distinctly elongate, ML/MW ratio 2.5-2.7. Promesonotum in dorsal view approximately 1.8 x as long as wide, pronotum convex in profile and rounded on sides (Figs. 1, 2). Anterolateral sides of pronotum convex, setose angulations or tubercles absent but anterolateral setae have base on sharp carina. Anterior margin of mesonotum excavated, thus appears bituberculate, protruding distinctly above the level of posterior part of pronotum. Propodeum elongated, approximately 1.18 x as long as wide. Propodeal spines moderately long, thin, at base only twice wider than at apex, acute apically, run slightly to moderately upwards (Figs. 2, 5, 6). Dorsal part of pronotum with diffused to distinct microreticulation and anteriorly and basally with few transverse rugae, sides of pronotum with diffused microreticulation, without or posteriorly with sparse, thin, mostly perpendicular rugae, surface appears shiny. Elevated part of mesonotum dorsally shiny with few transverse or partly irregular rugae, on sides with few longitudinal rugae, interspaces smooth or with diffused microreticulation, appears shiny (Fig. 2). Dorsal surface of propodeum anteriorly usually with short transverse rugae, sometimes with oblique or partly irregular rugae, between propodeal spines and on posterior slope smooth and shiny, in sides microreticulate, without rugae, only metapleural area with sharp longitudinal rugae and smooth and shiny interspaces. Propodeal spines moderately long, PSL/HW ratio 0.220–0.279 (mean 0.253). **Petiole.** Elongate with long peduncle, its anterior face deeply concave, node subangulate, PL/PH ratio 1.477–1.684 (mean 1.593). Ventral margin of petiole in the middle straight, shallowly concave before apex, without spine or angulation (Fig. 1). In dorsal view, petiole constricted at base then weakly divergent, almost parallel before petiolar node, then globular (Fig. 1). Base and ventral side distinctly microreticulated but without rugae, on sides and dorsally with diffused microreticulation to smooth and shiny, posterior face only at base with short, longitudinal rugae. **Postpetiole.** In lateral view rounded or slightly depressed at apex, in dorsal view approximately as long as wide with regularly rounded sides, PPW/PW ratio 1.184–0.324 (mean 1.250) (Fig. 1). Base, ventral side and dorsum of node diffusely microreticulated to smooth, shiny, posterior face distinctly microreticulated and on sides usually with short longitudinal rugae. **Gaster.** Smooth and shiny, only basal node with very short longitudinal rugae. **Legs.** Elongated, HFL/ML ratio 0.794–0.889 (mean 0.847), hind femora distinctly swollen in the middle, hind tibiae only slightly widened from base to apex. **Setosity.** Head in frontal view with numerous short, light yellow setae, the longest in the largest workers with length 0.175. Entire dorsum of pronotum and anterior part of mesonotum

with sparse, mixed short to moderately long, erect setae, the longest approximately as long as or slightly longer than erect setae on head, propodeum with only two pairs of short erect setae. Petiolar and postpetiolar nodes with 8-12 standing setae, slightly shorter than the longest setae on head and pronotum, gaster with moderately dense erect setae, as long as the longest setae on head (Fig. 1).

Range of the morphological variability. Variability within the studied series of *Aphaenogaster kurdica* is indistinct and manifested mostly in body size, shape of propodeal spines, sculpture of propodeum, and convexity of mesonotum and propodeum. In the palest specimens the whole body is yellowish, while in the darkest specimens, the body is yellowish ochraceous with slightly darker head and mesonotum. In the largest specimens anterior margin of mesonotum is strongly rising above the surface of pronotum, deeply excavate with well marked anterolateral angles forming a high tubercle, dorsal surface of propodeum is flat, with lateral margins sharp posteriorly, and long propodeal spines moderately directed upwards with PSL/HW ratio above 0.27 (Fig. 5), in the smallest specimens mesonotum is moderately rising above the surface of pronotum, shallowly excavate with anterolateral angles forming rather low angulation than high tubercle, dorsal surface of propodeum is convex, without sharp lateral margins posteriorly, and with short propodeal spines distinctly directed upwards with PSL/HW ratio below 0.23 (Fig. 6). Dorsal sculpture of propodeum varies from complete transverse to partly oblique or irregular.

Biological note. Ants were collected on trunk of *Carpinus betulus* L. tree in Tuskestan Forest (Figs. 7, 8).

A key to the *Aphaenogaster graeca* group

1. Dorsal surface of propodeum with mostly longitudinal rugae. Head and mesosoma reddish brown to pale brown, gaster uniformly black (Figs. 9, 10). Head longer, mean HL/HW ratio 1.304 (Fig. 15). Scape longer, SL/HW ratio 1.4-1.6. Western Turkey and Lesbos island of Aegean Greece ***A. aktaci* KIRAN & TEZCAN**
 — Dorsal surface of propodeum with mostly transverse rugae. Head and mesosoma from yellowish brown to dark brown, gaster not uniformly black (Figs. 1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 11-14). Head shorter, mean HL/HW ratio 1.165-1.205 (Figs 4, 16, 17). Scape shorter, SL/HW ratio 1.2-1.3 **2**
2. Base of the first gaster tergite with distinct rugae. Body brown to dark brown (Figs. 11, 12), head distinctly darker than mesosoma. Head sculpture strong, posterior part of head dorsum with sculpture only slightly reduced but still distinct, lateral surface of pronotum, at least partly, with strong longitudinal rugae (Fig. 16). Olympus Massif in Greece ***A. graeca* SCHULZ**
 — Base of the first gaster tergite smooth, at most basal node with very short longitudinal rugae. Body mostly yellowish-brown to rusty-brown (Figs. 1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 1, 14). Head sculpture weaker, posterior part of head dorsum with sculpture at least partly reduced, lateral surface of pronotum smooth or with few gentle longitudinal or perpendicular rugae (Figs. 4, 17) **3**
3. Scape shorter, mean SL/HW ratio 1.118. Head in frontal view usually subtrapezoidal, in anterior half with distinct background microreticulation thus surface appears slightly dull (Fig. 17). Propodeal spines relatively longer, PSL 0.263-0.378 (mean 0.313), mean PSL/HW ratio 0.277. Mountains of Bulgaria, Croatia, North Macedonia, northern Greece and Slovenia ***A. illyrica* BRAČKO *et al.***

— Scape longer, mean SL/HW ratio 1.252. Head in frontal view evenly rounded, in anterior half with diffused background microreticulation thus surface appears shiny (Fig. 4). Propodeal spines relatively shorter, PSL 0.180-0.320 (mean 0.255), mean PSL/HW ratio 0.253. Caucasian Russia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and northern Iran
 *A. kurdica* RUZSKY

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REFERENCES

- ALICATA A., SCHIFANI E. 2019. Three endemic *Aphaenogaster* from the Siculo-Maltese archipelago and the Italian Peninsula: part of a hitherto unrecognized species group from the Maghreb? (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmicinae). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 59: 1–16.
- ARAKELIAN G.R. 1994. Fauna of the Republic of Armenia. Hymenopterous insects. Ants (Formicidae). Erevan: Gitutium, 153 pp. [In Russian]
- ARNOLDI K.V. 1948. Ants of Talysh and the Diabar depression. Their importance for the characterization of communities of terrestrial invertebrates and for historical analysis of the fauna. *Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta. Akademiya Nauk SSSR* 7(2): 206–262.
- BOER P. 2013. Revision of the European ants of the *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa*-group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie* 156: 57–93.
- BOLTON B. 2024. An online catalog of the ants of the world. Available from <http://antcat.org> (accessed 2024-01-11).
- BOROWIEC L. 2014. Catalogue of ants of Europe, the Mediterranean Basin and adjacent regions (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* (monograph) 25: 1–340.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2014. Review of Mediterranean members of the *Aphaenogaster ceconii* group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), with description of four new species. *Zootaxa* 3861: 40–60.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2018. Notes on ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of Samos island, Greece. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 27(online 003): 1–13.
- BOROWIEC L., LAPEVA-GJONOVA A., SALATA S. 2019. Three species of *Aphaenogaster* MAYR, 1853 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) new to Bulgarian fauna. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 71: 613–616.
- BRAČKO G., LAPEVA-GJONOVA A., SALATA S., BOROWIEC L., POLAK S. 2019. *Aphaenogaster illyrica*, a new species from the mountains of the Balkan Peninsula (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *ZooKeys* 862: 89–107.
- DUBOVIKOFF D.A., YUSUPOV Z.M. 2017. 69. Family Formicidae – ants, pp. 197–210, In: BELOKOBYSKIY S.A., LELEJ A.S. (Eds.), Annotated Catalogue of the Hymenoptera of Russia, vol. 1 Symphyta and Apocrita: Aculeata, Proceedings of the Zoological Institute RAS, Supplement 6.
- EMERY C. 1908. Beiträge zur Monographie der Formiciden des paläarktischen Faunengebietes. (Hym.) (Fortsetzung.) III. Die mit *Aphaenogaster* verwandte Gattungengruppe. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift* 1908: 305–338.
- GALKOWSKI C., AUBERT C., BLATRIX R. 2019. *Aphaenogaster ichnusa* SANTSCHEI, 1925, bona species, and redescription of *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798) (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Sociobiology* 66: 420–425.
- GÓMEZ K., MARTÍNEZ D., ESPADALER X. 2018. Phylogeny of the ant genus *Aphaenogaster* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in the Iberian Peninsula, with the description of a new species. *Sociobiology* 65: 215–224.
- GRATIASHVILI N., BARJADZE SH. 2008. Checklist of the ants (Formicidae LATREILLE, 1809) of Georgia. *Proceedings of the Institute of Zoology* 23: 130–146.
- KIRAN K., AKTAÇ N., TEZCAN S. 2008. Three new species of ants (genus *Aphaenogaster*, Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Turkey. *Biología* (Bratislava) 63: 689–695.
- PAKNIA O., RADCHENKO A., ALIPANAH H., PFEIFFER M. 2008. A preliminary checklist of the ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of Iran. *Myrmecological News* 11: 151–159.
- RUZSKY M. 1905. The ants of Russia. (Formicariae Imperii Rossici). Systematics, geography and data on the biology of Russian ants. Part I. *Trudy Obshchestva Estestvoispytatelei pri Imperatorskom Kazanskom Universitete* 38: 1–800. [in Russian]
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2016. A new species of the *Aphaenogaster ceconii* group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Rhodes. *Zootaxa* 4170: 194–200.
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2018. Redescription of *Aphaenogaster muschtaidica* EMERY, 1908 with a key to *gibbosa* species group. *Asian Myrmecology* 10: e010002, 15 pp.
- SALATA S., KARAMAN C., KIRAN K., BOROWIEC L. 2021. Review of the *Aphaenogaster splendida* species-group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Annales Zoologici* 71: 297–343.

- SCHIFANI E., ALICATA A. 2023. Nomenclatural changes on some Mediterranean *Aphaenogaster* MAYR, 1853 taxa (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Zootaxa* 5277(1): 59–70.
- SCHIFANI E., ALICATA A., MENCHETTI M., BOROWIEC L., FISHER B.L., KARAMAN C., KIRAN K., OUESLATI W., SALATA S., BLATRIX R. 2022. Revisiting the morphological species groups of West-Palaeartic *Aphaenogaster* ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) under a phylogenetic perspective: toward an evolutionary classification. *Arthropod Systematics & Phylogeny* 80: 627–648.
- SCHULZ A. 1994. *Aphaenogaster graeca* nova species (Hym: Formicidae) aus dem Olymp-Gebirge (Griechenland) und eine Gliederung der Gattung *Aphaenogaster*. *Beiträge zur Entomologie* 44: 417–429.
- ZIĘCINA D., MENCHETTI M., BOROWIEC L., BRAČKO G., LAPEVA-GJONOVA A., VILA R., SALATA S. 2024. Taxonomic revision of the *Aphaenogaster subterranea* species group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Annales Zoologici* 74: 237–282.

Figs. 1–2. *Aphaenogaster kurdica* RUSZKY, worker: dorsal (1), lateral (2) (scale bar = 1 mm).
Photos by L. Borowiec.

Figs. 3–4. *Aphaenogaster kurdica* Ruzsky, worker: head and antennae (3), head sculpture (4) (scale bar = 1 mm). Photos by L. Borowiec.

Figs. 5–6. *Aphaenogaster kurdica* RUSZKY, body variation: the largest worker (5), the smallest worker (6) (scale bar = 1 mm). Photos by L. Borowiec.

Figs. 7–8. Habitat for *Aphaenogaster kurdica* RUSKY in Tuskestan forest close to Gorgan, Golestan Province, Iran. Photos by M. Yazdanian.

Figs. 9–10. *Aphaenogaster aktaci* KIRAN & TEZCAN, worker: dorsal (9), lateral (10) (scale bar = 1 mm). Photos by L. Borowiec.

Figs. 11–12. *Aphaenogaster graeca* SCHULZ, worker: dorsal (11), lateral (12) (scale bar = 1 mm). Photos by L. Borowiec.

Figs. 13–14. *Aphaenogaster illyrica* BRAČKO *et al.*, worker: dorsal (13), lateral (14) (scale bar = 1 mm). Photos by L. Borowiec.

Figs. 15–17. Worker head in frontal view: *Aphaenogaster aktaci* KIRAN & TEZCAN (15), *Aphaenogaster graeca* SCHULZ (16), *Aphaenogaster illyrica* BRAČKO *et al.* (17) (not in scale). Photos by L. Borowiec.

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